

Bashkir dialectal materials in the works of researchers of the 18th and the beginning of the 20th centuries

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Abstract: The article studies Bashkir dialect materials in the works of the 18th and the beginning of the 20th centuries. These materials act as comparative materials on Bashkir dialectology. The study of this topic identifies the diversity and richness of the Bashkir language and its dialects. The article analyzes the linguistic features of the works of A. G. Bessonov, V. Katarinsky, M. Bekchurin and others. Phonetic, morphological and lexical features of the texts of monuments of the 18th and the beginning of the 20th centuries are considered in comparison with the data of modern dialects and the literary Bashkir language.

Keywords: Dialect, literary language, the Bashkir language, history of the language, written monuments, A. G. Bessonov, M. Bekchurin, V. Katarinsky.

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Introduction

The study of Bashkir dialects has a long history. It is proved by the works of researchers of the Bashkirs and the Bashkir language of the 18th and the beginning of the 20th centuries. It contains dialect materials of both lexical and grammatical types. For example, in a handwritten dictionary of the 18th century Mendiya Bekchurin's "Translation of words into the Bashkir language" recorded the following lexemes: anai, inai, apasai 'mother' and in literary language asai; dzhanlyk 'beast' and in literary language yanlek; buta 'belt' and in literary language bilbau; sygyr/syjyr 'cow' and in literary language hyjyr and others [Ishberdin, 1986, p. 11].

Dialectal material for almost all territorial groups of the Bashkirs is present in the "Initial Guide to the Study of Arabic, Persian and Tatar Languages with the dialects of the Bukharans, Bashkirs, Kirghiz and residents of Turkistan" by Mirsalih Biksurin. It was written by him in the middle of the 19th century. In Mirsalih Biksurin's work the samples of Bashkir speech are of particular value for dialectology. They reflect not only the lexical, but also the morphological features of the dialect. For example, in the fairy tale "Batyr batsha akiyate" ("The Tale of Tsar Peter") the following lexemes are recorded in one form or another: darandar 'companions' and in the literary language yarandar; uynnar 'games' and in the literary language uyndar; tashap 'having thrown' and in the literary language tashlap, etc.

"In the work Initial Guide..." by Mirsalikh Bikchurin the phonetic features of the Bashkir dialects are also reflected. For

example, the reflex of the common Turkic sound 's' in the intervocalic position in the "Initial Guide..." is represented by the sounds s, th and h. They are basyp - bathyp, bahyp and in literary language bathyp; iserek - itherek - iherek and in literary language itherek and others [Bikchurin, 1869].

Dialectal materials dating back to the late 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries are presented to the missionary literature of the Translation Commission of the Orthodox Missionary Society at the Brotherhood of St. Gurius in Kazan. This commission prepared and published the following primers and dictionaries as well as the first translations of liturgical, instructive and educational books: "A Brief Russian-Bashkir Dictionary" [Bashkir-Russian Dictionary, 1899], "Bashkir Proverbs of M. Kuvatov" [Kuvatov, 1895, pp. 31-48], "The Life of the Holy Great Martyr and Healer Panteleimon, Liturgy of St. John Chrysostom" in the Bashkir and Kazakh languages [Translation Commission, 1901, p. 60], "ABC for the Bashkirs" [Bukvat' dlya Bashkir, 1892, 1898, 1907, 1908], "The Holy Gospel of Matthew (experience)" [The Holy Gospel of Matthew, 1899], "About the afterlife" [Translation Commission, 1901, p. 66], "The Holy Gospel of Matthew, Mark, Luke and John" [The Holy Gospel of Matthew, 1902], "The first book after the ABC book for reading and practical initial lessons of the Russian language for the south-eastern Bashkirs" [Bessonov, 1907, p. 56].

Based on a preliminary linguistic analysis of several monuments it was established that for most of them material from individual dialects of the Bashkir language was used. For example, in the "First Book after the ABC Book," the author notes that "the

Bashkir language was divided into several dialects (up to 5)" and "the first edition of these books made only in one of these dialects, in the dialect of the Bashkirs of the southeastern part of the Orsk district" [Bessonov, 1907, p. 55]. In our opinion, the most valuable dialect material of the works of the 19th century is contained in the dictionaries of V. Katarinsky. V. Katarinsky draws the attention of readers in the "Bashkir-Russian Dictionary" to the dialectal variants of some lexemes. For example: agay "akay - agay in kat. volost" [Bashkir-Russian dictionary, 1889, p. 4], azal 'death' and in literary language azhal; bire 'demon' and in literary language barey; mirgirthir jylan 'horned snake' and in literary language mirgirthir jylan; hothay sasage 'pox of God' and in literary language hothay saskahe and others. It is interesting to note that V.V. Katarinsky associates individual dialects with certain tribal groups of the Bashkirs. For example, when presenting the word balga 'hammer' V. Katarinsky writes that it is used in the Katayskaya volost. While in other places the word sukesh functions [Bashkir-Russian dictionary, 1889, p. 26].

The importance of these publications for studying the history of the Bashkir language, its dialectology and other Turkic languages has been repeatedly emphasized in scientific literature. In fact, within the framework of the activities of the Translation Commission the first writing in Cyrillic was created. At that time first primers, dictionaries and grammars in the Bashkir language were developed.

In terms of studying the Bashkir dialects, the works of the Russian missionary, linguist and ethnographer Alexander Grigorievich Bessonov are of particular interest. It is important to emphasize that A. G. Bessonov was an educated person, who had an advanced level the Bashkir, Kazakh, Tatar and Udmurt languages.

In 1881, A. G. Bessonov wrote an article "On the dialects of the Kazan Tatar dialect and its relationship to the dialects and languages closest to it" [Bessonov, 1881, pp. 200-242]. The article presents a detailed description of the sound composition, grammatical structure and lexical features of the Bashkir and Tatar languages with their main dialects. The work of A. G. Bessonov became a kind of the first scientific analysis. It reflects with a high degree of accuracy the dialectal features of the Bashkir language, especially in the field of phonetics. In addition, in the article of A. G. Bessonov it was made an attempt to classify the dialects and subdialects of the Bashkir language.

In the texts of Bessonov the features of the Bashkir language are reflected as of the beginning of the 20th century. The main works of A. G. Bessonov, are his "ABC Book for the Bashkirs" [Bessonov, 1907, p. 47], "The First Book after the ABC Book for Reading and Initial Lessons of the Russian Language for the South-Eastern Bashkirs" [Bessonov, 1907, p. 56]. The linguistic data of the "ABC Book for the Bashkirs" (Kazan, 1907) were subjected to detailed examination [Ekba et al., 2019, pp. 101-111]. Let us briefly dwell on the main dialectal features that were identified on the basis of the linguistic analysis of the text of this monument.

During the study it was established that the "ABC" is based on two different dialects. The main text of the "ABC" is written in a dialect that is called by the author "the dialect of the northern part of Trans-Ural Bashkiria". For individual forms for comparison (in brackets) the author gives forms of "the dialect of the southern part of Trans-Ural Bashkiria". The third dialect called eastern (or

Kataysky) is also singled out as independent. In the final part of the ABC the text of the fairy tale is given in three dialects: northern, southern and eastern (Kataysky). An analysis of the graphic and phonetic features of the "ABC" made it possible to bring the main northern dialect closer to the Argayash dialect of the modern Bashkir language. The implementation of literary th, thl, thg as tht, thk, in the intervocalic position in place of the Proto-Turkic *-s- as well as in the modern Argayash dialect can be voiced and turn into -d-. This phenomenon is characteristic of the Argayash dialect as opposed to other eastern dialects. In some cases, the Proto-Turkic *-s- is preserved as an interdental th, which most likely may indicate that the process of voicing was just beginning in the time of A. G. Bessonov and occurred at a later period. The dialect designated by the author as southern according to a number of features was able to be correlated with the Kyzyl dialect of the eastern dialect. To confirm the validity of such a comparison the main morphological and morphological features of the "ABC" were examined in detail. In the course of the analysis of the morphophonological level of a number of word forms the consistent use of a special form of affixes characteristic of the eastern dialect was determined in contrast to the literary norm which adopted the forms of the southern dialect with affixes with the initial -l [Grammar of the modern Bashkir language, 1981, pp. 171, 228].: Cf.:

NomAbstr *-lyk: dustyk 'friendship' (lit. duthlyk),yalokudyk 'laziness' (lit. yalkauyk)

Adj *-ly: ukymyshty 'scholar' (lit. ukymyshly), tordo 'different' (lit. tirlir)

ConV *-lap: iptap 'be careful' (lit. iplap), uydap 'thinking' (lit. uylap)

PartPast *-lagan: bashtagan (lit. bashlagan) 'began, begun', uydagan (lit. uylagan) 'thought, thought'

Imp 2 Sing *-la: tashtama 'don't throw it away' (lit. tashlama), urdama (lit. urlama) 'don't steal' and many others. etc.

This system of affixes is characteristic of all forms of the dialects presented in the ABC both northern and southern. In addition, the monument notes a distinctive feature of the dialect of the Katai Bashkirs [Maksyutova, 1976, p. 16] which is not found in any other dialects or subdialects. The most significant feature that distinguishes the Yalan-Katai subdialect of the eastern dialect and the middle Karaidel dialects of the southern dialect from those considered above is the special form of affixes which after sonorants have a voiced form in -t- in contrast to the lit. voiced -l/d- [Mirzhanova, 1979, p. 98; Maksyutova, 1976, p. 104] and northern and southern, eastern dialects in -d:

Abl *-dan: urmantan (north., south. urmandan, lit. urmandan) 'from the forest'

Adj *-li: shikelte (northern shikelde, southern shikelde, lit. shikelte) 'like'

Imp 2Sing *-la: gorana (southern goranda, lit. hirana) 'shout'

PartPast *-lagan: gorantagan (southern gorandagan, lit. hiranlagan) 'screamed'.

In a more general form, the distribution of this feature in Bashkir dialects and subdialects was examined by F. G. Khisamitdinova. She notes that such a dialectal feature as the voiceless stage of the alternations l/t/d/b, n/t/d/b and q/k/u/g

occurring after the liquid 'r' and 'l' does not correlate with the modern boundaries of the dialects and subdialects of the Bashkir language, but is quite well connected with the territory of settlement of the Bashkir tribes of Katay, Tabyñ and Balyksy" [Khisamitdinova, 1989, p. 81]. For example, jamkyr 'rain', tamqa 'tamga', sanqa 'skis', jenka 'daughter-in-law', anta 'there', mynta 'here', kiltem 'I came, arrived', ungyk 'we were lucky', kulta 'in hand', kontoth 'during the day', uramka 'outside', boronko 'ancient', irtanke 'morning', kemka 'to whom', bartym 'I went'.

The dialectal features of the "ABC" in the field of morphology were noted for the use of the verbal infinitive ending in -iu: ariu 'to get tired', kijiñ 'to cut', as well as the imperative (2PI) ending in -in/on: iskindirin 'unfasten', toron 'stand still', which are characteristic of all dialects of the eastern dialect [Maksyutova, 1976, pp. 195, 197]. Another feature of the eastern dialect is associated with the use of the future tense affix ending in -ap. This feature is an important dialectal trait of the Argayash and Salzigut dialects which distinguishes them from the Miass, Kyzyl dialects, and literary Yakhyk. For example: -im, -iryñ in aisk dialect, -ir/-er in in miass d., -ilyr in kyz. d. [Maksyutova, 1976, pp. 54, 134, 194, 233, 276], eshetarin and in literary language ishetheren 'you will hear'. The system of pronouns presented in the "ABC" also has specific features of the eastern dialect. For example: anyñ 'his' and in literary language unyñ; alardyn 'their' and in literary language ularthyn; anan 'from him' and in literary language unan; alardan 'from them' and in literary language alarthan; a, al 'that' and in literary language ul 'that'. A number of dialecticisms characteristic of the eastern dialects were also found in the text of the ABC book.

A small part of the Bashkir texts collected by A. G. Bessonov is currently being studied. S. N. Muratov discovered a Bashkir text and a translation of one fairy tale in A. G. Bessonov's recording in the Collection of Manuscripts of the Leningrad Branch of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the USSR Academy of Sciences. They were transferred in 1961 to the Manuscript Department by the Archive of Orientalists at the Department from the fund of Academician V. V. Radlov. The text of the fairy tale in Russian transcription and its translation are currently stored there. This text was included by A. G. Bessonov in the section he called "Section 1: Tales of the Bashkirs of the Orsk District and the Tamyano-Tongaur volost of the Verkhneural'sk District". The text has two titles: 1) "The Depraved Father" and 2) "The Depraved Mother". A. G. Bessonov associates this text with the mountain dialect of the Bashkir language. The author emphasizes an interesting phenomenon inherent in the Bashkir language, when it is very difficult to hear a vowel sound between an occlusive consonant and a sonorant: 'blan' instead of 'belan', etc. In the text the author denotes some sounds with the letter zh: zhibyar 'let me go', zhoriy 'walking', zhort 'house', zheget 'fellow', zhir 'earth', etc. The research of Vilmos Prohle and his "Bashkir-Magyar Dictionary" are of interest to us in terms of studying Bashkir dialectology. In 1901, Vilmos Prohle arrived in the Ufa province to study the Bashkir language. As the author himself wrote: "I began to study the language in the summer of 1901 when I was on a study trip to the Ufa province at the expense of the Ministry of Religion and Public Education" [Prohle Vilmos, 1913, p. 194]. The author's first work was devoted to the study of the phonetic and morphological features of the Bashkir language [Prohle Vilmos, 1913, pp. 194-214]. In Volume 5 of the journal "Kelete Szemele" Vilmos Prohle's "Bashkir-Magyar Dictionary" was published

[Prohle Vilmos, 1913, pp. 228-271]. In the dictionary the author describes language units that reflect the basic lexical composition of the Bashkir language. The analysis of this work shows that the dictionary contains a sufficient number of dialect lexemes. Ex.: boya 'bika' (bull), boron 'orr' (nose), burange 'burgonya' (potato), gumba 'gomba' (mushrooms), hantuk, sandek 'lada' (box), hanrau, sanrau 'tompa' (voiceless), belan 'es' (conjunctions 'with', 'and'), etc. In general, individual dialectal features of the Bashkir language were reflected to one degree or another in the works of researchers of the 18th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, so we can rightfully call this period the first stage in the development of Bashkir dialectology.

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